

QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE POWER & ENERGY SYSTEMS

Opportunities, roadblocks, and a call to action from Quantum4EnergyNL

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The report was co-authored by N. Paterakis (TU Eindhoven), P. P. Vergara (TU Delft), M. Möller (TU Delft), J. Sallou (Wageningen University & Research), and M. Gerards (University of Twente).

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1. Summary

The transformation of power & energy systems is placing extraordinary demands on measurement, cybersecurity, and computational capabilities. As power & energy systems become more interconnected, digitalised, and constrained by geo-strategic and sustainability objectives, conventional approaches are increasingly reaching their fundamental limits. Quantum technologies offer a fundamentally different paradigm to address these limitations across sensing, communications, and computing.

This report assesses the potential role of quantum technologies in power & energy systems, with a focus on the Dutch research and innovation landscape. Drawing on an analysis of the international literature and research projects, together with insights from a national expert workshop organised by Quantum4EnergyNL, it finds that although the field has grown rapidly internationally since 2022, it remains an emerging research domain that has not yet reached structural maturity. In the Netherlands, several relevant activities are underway in both academia and industry at an exploratory level, but systematic investigation is lacking, especially compared with other European countries and the US.

A key insight is that the primary bottleneck is not just the maturity of quantum technologies, but also the absence of clearly defined, high-impact use cases grounded in actual power & energy system needs that would pull research in this domain. While research activity is growing rapidly, efforts in the Netherlands remain fragmented and often disconnected from operational challenges in the energy sector. The report highlights a staged pathway for impact across quantum sensing, communications, and computing for power & energy systems applications. In the near term, quantum sensing emerges as the most immediately applicable of quantum technologies, with applications in grid monitoring, underground asset localisation, and fault detection. In parallel, quantum communications, particularly post-quantum cryptography, address urgent cybersecurity needs for increasingly digitalised critical infrastructure. Quantum computing is expected to deliver value in the medium to long term, initially through hybrid quantum-classical approaches targeting complex optimisation and planning problems such as congestion management, real-time optimal power flow, and electricity market operations.

The report also identifies structural challenges that may hinder progress. These include a gap in cross-domain expertise, limited academia-industry collaboration in this area, and a mismatch between funding instruments and technology readiness levels. The latter leaves application-driven research in this emerging field insufficiently supported, in contrast with countries such as the US and Germany. Internationally, coordinated programmes are emerging, while efforts in the Netherlands remain comparatively dispersed despite strong underlying capabilities in both quantum technologies and energy systems research.

To unlock the potential of quantum technologies for the Energy Transition, the report calls for targeted, use-case-driven research funding, investment in multidisciplinary talent development, and structured collaboration across academia, industry, and other relevant stakeholders. The Netherlands is, in principle, well positioned given its strong quantum and energy research ecosystems, but early strategic action will be critical to ensure it will not only become competitive but takes on a leading role in this emerging field.

2. Power & energy systems in transition

Electrical power systems are among the most complex engineered cyber-physical systems ever created (Figure 1), and their reliable and efficient operation is a prerequisite for a functional and prosperous society. They encompass the generation, transmission, distribution, and end-use of electrical energy, built upon interconnected physical infrastructure that is interwoven with an ICT layer, and shaped by market-based operation, environmental constraints, and social and ethical dimensions, all of which are further influenced by geo-political forces. Other energy carriers, including natural gas, heat, and fuels, as well as sectors and infrastructures such as transportation, water, and logistics, are increasingly integrated and rely on electrical power systems as their backbone.

The next generation of power systems faces a set of deeply intertwined challenges. At their core, power systems must become truly reliable, affordable, and sustainable. These objectives are difficult to meet simultaneously, and current systems do not yet achieve them in full. However, achieving them is inseparable from Europe's legally binding commitments. The European Climate Law¹ enshrines the obligation for Europe's economy and society to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% compared with 1990 levels by 2030. The Fit for 55² legislative package provides the concrete instruments to realise these objectives across all major sectors of the economy, thereby putting the power system at the centre of Europe's transformation agenda.

Delivering on these objectives requires a fundamental transformation of how power systems are designed and operated. The consensus outlook for future power systems points towards deep integration across energy carriers and sectors, full digitalisation enabling automated infrastructure management and control, market-driven stakeholder interaction through efficient pan-European and local markets, and the strategic upgrade and expansion of energy infrastructure³.

Technically, achieving this vision places stringent demands on the measurement, cybersecurity, and computational capabilities that underpin power & energy systems. **Complex computation** is ubiquitous across the power system stack, from real-time operational analysis and network optimisation to the diagnostic and predictive analytics needed to manage an increasingly dynamic grid. Yet **computation carries an energy footprint of its own**, creating a tension between computational ambition and the sustainability objectives that power systems are meant to serve. At the same time, critical infrastructure demands **cybersecurity** that is not only adequate today but also future-proof against threats that have not yet fully emerged. **High-fidelity metrology** is equally foundational: precise, trustworthy measurement supports everything from grid stability to market settlements and asset management.

Addressing these challenges is not only a matter of technical progress that will make a success of the Energy Transition, but also of strategic relevance: the ability of the Netherlands and Europe to develop, deploy, and govern the next generation of power system technologies is key to technological sovereignty and long-term regional resilience.

Figure 1: Dimensions influencing electrical power system development

¹ Regulation (EU) 2021/1119

² <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/fit-for-55/>

³ ETIP SNET, [Vision 2050 - Integrating smart networks for the Energy Transition: serving society and protecting the environment](#)

3. Quantum technologies for power & energy systems

Quantum technologies are maturing and offer potential solutions across computing, sensing, and communications. A new research area has emerged internationally in recent years, investigating how quantum technologies can play a transformative role in power engineering. Figure 2 shows a breakdown of quantum technologies with illustrative applications related to power & energy systems.

Using published literature as a proxy for the state and momentum of the field, Figure 3 shows the number of publications related to quantum computing for power & energy systems between 2019 and February 2026⁴ as a characteristic example. It can be seen that prior to 2022, publication counts were negligible, but they have risen sharply since then. The growing volume of publications is consistent with the maturation and broader availability of cloud-based quantum computing platforms, which have lowered the entry barrier for power systems researchers.

Applications of quantum computing have been explored across all areas of interest in power & energy systems:

- Power & energy system analysis and control, i.e., the study and assessment of energy systems to ensure reliable and efficient operation under normal and fault conditions. The main motivation is the complexity of solving large-scale systems of nonlinear algebraic and differential equations that lie at the core of analysis and control tasks.
- Power & energy system optimisation, i.e., the determination of the most efficient, reliable and cost-effective operation and planning of energy systems subject to techno-economic constraints. The main motivation is that optimisation problems of practical interest are constrained, mixed-integer in nature, and large-scale, owing to factors such as detailed infrastructure and uncertainty modelling.
- Diagnostic and predictive analytics for power & energy systems (e.g., renewables' forecasting). The main motivation is the high dimensionality and uncertainty of the underlying data, where quantum machine learning may offer advantages in feature representation and probabilistic forecasting.

Figure 2: Quantum technologies and illustrative applications in power systems

Figure 3: Number of publications on quantum computing for power & energy systems

⁴ The literature search considered publications indexed by Scopus (conference and journal papers, and preprints) with a cut-off date of February 10, 2026. Studies addressing quantum computing / algorithms and power systems were classified as relevant. Studies related to quantum-inspired algorithms, quantum sensing, communications, cryptography, etc., were excluded.

In parallel, the energy industry is also exploring quantum technology use cases. For instance, the Distribution System Operator (DSO) Alliander runs a portfolio of exploratory projects in the fields of quantum computing⁵ and sensing⁶, in partnership with TNO and Capgemini. Quantum technologies have also been included in the E.DSO Technology Radar⁷.

The number of relevant research projects has also been increasing globally. [Table 1](#) presents a non-exhaustive overview of relevant research projects internationally. A growing number of dedicated mission-driven programmes have emerged in the US, the UK, and Australia, focused on energy system modelling and optimisation as well as energy infrastructure cybersecurity. This indicates that power & energy systems have been recognised as an impactful application area for quantum technologies, and that a rapidly developing international research agenda is forming at the intersection of quantum technologies and the Energy Transition. Within Europe, Germany is leading, whereas EU- and NL-funded projects remain conspicuously absent.

Quantum technologies and sustainability

As discussed earlier in this report, the computational resources required to manage increasingly complex power & energy systems carry an energy footprint of their own. Quantum technologies sit on both sides of this tension: as a potential tool for advancing sustainability objectives, and as a technology whose own environmental impact must be understood. Quantum computing is increasingly explored to address sustainability challenges that are computationally intractable for classical systems, including the optimisation of energy grids, improved climate modelling, and the simulation of novel materials for batteries⁸. These application-side opportunities are a core motivation for the research agenda outlined in this report.

At the same time, the sustainability of quantum computing itself has only recently begun to receive scientific attention. The energetic costs of quantum technologies have received comparatively little attention in deployment strategies⁹. Current quantum systems consume far less power than classical supercomputers, roughly 25 kW for superconducting platforms and 7 kW for neutral-atom systems versus over 21 MW for leading supercomputers¹⁰. However, cryogenic cooling dominates the energy budget and scales sensitively with architecture and qubit count¹¹. Whether this translates into a genuine efficiency gain depends on the problem: for current Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) hardware, classical methods can be more energy-efficient¹², but a quantum energy advantage could materialise before a computational advantage does, for specific problem classes^{13,14}. Full life-cycle assessments covering embodied carbon, rare materials, and electronic waste are still in their infancy^{15,16,17}, and standardised sustainability benchmarks do not yet exist¹⁸. [Integrating sustainability considerations into quantum research agendas from the outset would help ensure that quantum technologies make a net positive contribution to the Energy Transition.](#)

⁵ QReorder, [Quantum computing for power grid analysis and simulation](#)

⁶ A quantum sensing exploration with Alliander on cable selection and load detection. TNO R10008, 2026

⁷ [E.DSO Technology Radar](#), 2025

⁸ Ho et al., "Quantum computing for climate resilience and sustainability challenges", arXiv:2407.16296, 2024

⁹ A. Auffèves, "Quantum technologies need a quantum energy initiative", PRX Quantum, 2022

¹⁰ PASQAL, ["Quantum computing: rethinking energy consumption"](#), PASQAL Blog, 2025

¹¹ M.J. Martin et al., "Energy use in quantum data centers: scaling the impact of computer architecture, qubit performance, size, and thermal parameters", IEEE Trans. Sust. Comp., 2022

¹² D. Jaschke and S. Montangero, "Is quantum computing green? An estimate for an energy-efficiency quantum advantage", Quant. Sci. Tech., 2023

¹³ F. Meier and H. Yamasaki, "Energy-consumption advantage of quantum computation", PRX Energy, 2025

¹⁴ M. Fellous-Asiani et al., "Optimizing resource efficiencies for scalable full-stack quantum computers", PRX Quantum, 2023

¹⁵ N. Arora and P. Kumar, "Sustainable quantum computing", Comm. ACM, 2025

¹⁶ S. Cordier et al., "Scaling up to problem sizes: an environmental life cycle assessment of quantum computing", arXiv:2411.00118, 2024

¹⁷ E. O. Esho et al., "Sustainable generative AI and quantum computing: review assessment on the environmental impact of generative AI and quantum technologies", Front. Sustain., 2026

¹⁸ S. Chen, "Are quantum computers really energy efficient?", Nat. Comp. Sci., 2023

Table 1: Overview of research projects at the intersection of quantum technologies and power & energy systems

Year	Project	Short description	Funding amount	Funding instrument	Country
2020	Fundamental modeling of power economics with quantum algorithms (EnerQuant)	Exploratory research in quantum computing for energy system modelling	€ 2M	Federal Ministry of Economics and Energy	Germany
2021	Application of quantum computers for the optimization of future energy grids (Q-GRID)	Viability of quantum computing for energy network optimization problems	€ 2.8M	Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space	
2023	Quantum technologies for energy grids (QuGrids)	Quantum computing and communication for energy system planning and operation	€ 3M	Ministry of Culture and Science of North Rhine-Westphalia	
2024	Applications, interfaces and data formats for quantum computing algorithms in energy system modelling (Attract'em)	Quantum computing for energy system planning and operation	n/a	DLR Quantum Computing Initiative	
2023	Post quantum cryptography framework for energy aware contexts (PQ-REACT)	Post quantum cryptography for smart grid applications (pilot)	€ 5.3M	Horizon Europe	EU / international
2025	Smart Grid Management	Hybrid quantum-classical optimization for the unit commitment problem	n/a	CERN Open Quantum Institute	Switzerland / international
2026	A Quantum Computing-Based Demonstrator for Remote Community Energy System	Quantum optimization for remote community energy system management	AU\$ 1.4M	Critical Technologies Challenge Program (Department of Industry, Science and Resources)	Australia
2026	Quantum Enhanced Optimisation for Energy Efficient Data Centres	Hybrid quantum-classical optimization for data centre cooling efficiency	AU\$ 1.1M		
2024	Grid research, integration and deployment for quantum (GRID-Q)	Identification of use cases for quantum computing, communication and sensing on the power grid	US\$ 3.7M	DOE	US
2025	QuantumGrid Innovation Hub	Quantum computing and networking test bed for the development of quantum applications for grid security and related approaches	US\$ 1.3M	NSF Directorate for Technology, Innovation and Partnerships	
2026	Enhancing neutral-atom computers for optimizing delivery of energy (ENCODE)	Quantum computing system and algorithmic toolset for generation unit scheduling optimization	US\$ 6.2M	ARPA-Energy	
2023	Quantum computing solutions for optimization problems in energy grids	Quantum algorithms for optimization problems in energy grid operations	£ 1.2 M	Innovate UK (Quantum Catalyst Fund)	UK
2024	Benchmarking Quantum Advantage	Quantum computing approaches for optimal power flow and short-term forecasting	£ 498k	EPSRC	
2025	Quantum Utilisation for Breakthroughs in Ireland's Computing (QUBIC)	Power system optimization and forecasting algorithms (and other domains)	€ 13.7 M	Disruptive Technologies Innovation Fund	IE
2022-2026	Alliander, TNO, OAL, Capgemini collaborative projects	Various projects on quantum computing and sensing for distribution systems	n/a	n/a	NL
2024	Quantum-assisted stochastic programming accelerating the energy transition (QUASAR)	Hybrid quantum-classical optimization for power system problems	€ 85k	SURF Open Call grant 2023	

4. The Quantum4EnergyNL initiative

The Netherlands is strongly positioned in research and development across both quantum technologies and the Energy Transition.

Quantum technology is one of the ten key enabling technologies in the National Technology Strategy, with a dedicated roadmap outlined in the National Agenda on Quantum Technologies¹⁹. These priorities are backed by QDNL²⁰, which aims to build a quantum innovation ecosystem, and by Holland High Tech, which drives public-private partnerships through its Strategic Programme for Quantum Technologies²¹.

On the energy side, the Netherlands Energy Research Alliance (NERA)²² brings together Dutch academic research organisations conducting energy research, coordinating their efforts and positioning Dutch energy research internationally. The national research funder NWO supports this through its dedicated Energy Transition programme²³, funding fundamental and applied research.

However, efforts at the intersection between quantum technologies and power systems, while present, are developing in parallel and remain neither well-coordinated nor highly visible, either at a national or at a European level.

Quantum4EnergyNL emerged as an initiative of researchers across the 4TU (TU Eindhoven, TU Delft, Wageningen University & Research, and University of Twente) to address this gap. It fosters a cross-disciplinary community of experts approaching quantum technology applications for power systems from both Electrical Engineering and ICT perspectives. Its ambition is to boost the visibility and coordination of related research efforts through dedicated activities.

Specifically, Quantum4EnergyNL aims to:

- Jointly assess the research landscape in the Netherlands, identify strategic gaps, and pinpoint application areas where the 4TU can lead.
- Produce a joint research agenda that accounts for the unique expertise and ambition of academic partners and aligns with industry needs.
- Pave the way for a long-term collaboration platform that can serve as a springboard for interdisciplinary national and European projects on quantum technologies for power & energy systems.

Quantum4EnergyNL is supported by the 4TU Centre for Energy (4TU.Energy) and the Netherlands Institute for Research on ICT (4TU.NIRICT).

¹⁹ <https://www.kia-st.nl/en/kia-key-enabling-technologies/sleuteltechnologieen-kets/quantum-technologies-key-enabling-technologies>

²⁰ <https://qdnl.nl/>

²¹ <https://hollandhightech.nl/en/programmes-and-projects/strategic-programmes/quantum-technologies>

²² <https://www.nera.nl/>

²³ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/overview-pages/energy-transition>

5. Community perspectives - Expert Workshop

On March 4, 2026, Quantum4EnergyNL held a full-day expert workshop in Utrecht to:

- Connect researchers and practitioners interested in or working on applications of quantum technologies for power & energy systems.
- Map relevant past and ongoing research projects in the Netherlands and abroad.
- Identify areas and challenges in the Energy Transition where quantum technologies can have meaningful impact.
- Explore barriers and opportunities for programmatic research.

The workshop drew 28 participants who engaged in an interactive plenary session, thematic breakouts in four independent groups, and two synthesis sessions (Figure 4).

This report was compiled using input from the workshop and circulated to participants for feedback.

5.1 Participants' profile

Figure 5 shows the distribution of workshop participants by sector and role. Workshop participants were predominantly from universities and system operators, with the majority identifying as applied researchers, innovation managers, or business developers. Their primary technical domains were found to be balanced across power & energy systems, computer science / ICT systems, and quantum technologies. The workshop brought together a group with complementary expertise across both the power & energy and quantum technologies domains: 62% of participants reported working knowledge or higher in both, and over half indicated that their organisation is already engaging in relevant research.

Figure 4: Quantum4EnergyNL workshop March 4, 2026.

Figure 5: Distribution of workshop participants by sector and by role.

5.2 Workshop insights

Question 1: Which key challenges in power systems could be addressed by quantum technologies?

The discussion prioritised quantum technologies based on their expected impact and readiness for deployment in power & energy systems. The findings point to a staged evolution, with quantum sensing as the most immediate opportunity, followed by quantum communications and, in the longer term, quantum computing for complex optimisation problems.

Quantum sensing

Participants across all four breakout groups identified quantum sensing as the most near-term applicable technology. Specific challenges raised repeatedly included fault detection in underground cables and transformers, the localisation of buried assets such as cables and gas pipes, and non-invasive grid measurements and monitoring. Participants regarded quantum sensing as the most technologically mature quantum capability and the one that directly addresses asset management challenges that power system stakeholders face.

Quantum communications

Some participants identified post-quantum cryptography as an immediate priority, given the urgency to provide robust cybersecurity for infrastructure that is becoming increasingly digitalised and more exposed to cyber threats.

In the medium term, quantum networking could contribute to secure power system communications through quantum key distribution for data exchange among grid operators and other power system stakeholders.

Quantum computing

Participants noted that transformative quantum computing for power & energy system applications is likely to remain a decade or more away. However, there is strong short-term interest in exploring use cases, deepening the understanding of the potential of quantum computing for power & energy engineering applications, and actively developing new algorithmic approaches for problems inspired by the Energy Transition.

Medium-term expectations are dominated by operational optimisation and planning problems addressed through hybrid quantum-classical algorithms. The first real use cases of quantum computing as a useful subroutine (e.g., graph optimisation within a larger classical workflow) are expected to emerge in this period. Participants broadly converged on problems such as real-time optimal power flow and reliability calculations, network reconfiguration, resource scheduling, and grid planning. These problems are closely related to major socio-technical challenges such as congestion management. Electricity markets are another area where quantum optimisation could prove transformative. For instance, by enabling scalable market clearing algorithms, energy sharing among distributed prosumers, and electric vehicle fleet coordination.

In the longer term, participants envision full-scale quantum computing applied to constrained optimisation problems, large-scale power flow and reliability analysis, partial differential equation solvers (e.g., heat equations for cable modelling and power system dynamics), complex multi-physics simulations, decentralised resource coordination, and climate-driven energy system modelling.

Question 2: What are the two highest-impact use cases where quantum technologies could create measurable value?

Each group was asked to identify two high-impact use cases where quantum technologies could create measurable value. Participants discussed a broad range of specific power & energy system applications. This signals a broader awareness that quantum technologies can make an impact in many parts of the energy value chain as they mature. Across the four discussion groups, two use cases surfaced consistently. The first reflects the relative maturity of the underlying quantum technology, while the second reflects the societal urgency of the power system problem it addresses.

Use case 1: quantum sensing for grid asset monitoring and fault detection

Quantum sensing for grid asset monitoring and fault detection was the most consistently and thoroughly discussed use case. Participants highlighted specific applications including non-intrusive monitoring and localisation of underground cables and pipes, early detection of faults and defects before they cause outages, improved sensor precision through the fusion of multiple quantum sensors, and accurate mapping of underground infrastructure.

Why it is considered high impact: medium- and low-voltage electrical distribution systems rely on underground assets. These assets are costly and disruptive to inspect, while measurements are typically limited to substations, with little or no monitoring along the cables themselves. As these assets age, quantum sensors could provide insights into their condition without the need for excavation.

Quantifiable success metrics: reduced unplanned outages, faster fault response times, a larger share of grid assets accurately mapped, and improved sensor sampling precision.

Use case 2: combinatorial optimisation for congestion management

Grid congestion was one of the most frequently cited challenges across all groups, and several developed the topic into a full use case. Specific applications discussed included real-time generation and demand redispatch optimisation, dynamic network reconfiguration based on real-time congestion data, and strategic planning of grid expansion.

Why it is considered high impact: the optimisation problems underlying congestion management are typically multi-objective and non-convex, making them computationally challenging at large network scale or under uncertainty. Participants indicated that even modest improvements in the use of existing network capacity and available flexibility could reduce investments in new infrastructure.

Quantifiable success metrics: reduced congestion management costs, lower capital expenditure on network reinforcement and expansion, and a higher utilisation rate of existing grid capacity and flexibility resources.

Beyond congestion management, some groups emphasised that quantum computing does not need to solve entirely new problems to create value. Rather, faster solutions to existing problems, when applied alongside classical approaches, may be enough to make it viable in an operational context. Specific applications included real-time optimal power flow and fast decision-making for network operators and electricity market participants. In other words, improvements in computational speed and scale are seen as distinct value drivers for quantum computing.

Question 3: What are the main barriers to adopting quantum technologies for the use cases identified in Questions 1 and 2?

Participants were asked to consider the factors that hinder the adoption of quantum technologies, including technical maturity, infrastructure access, skills gap, and business case uncertainty. A summary of the barriers that were identified is provided below.

Technology readiness

Hardware and algorithmic limitations make it difficult to justify near-term focus on this field and they hinder early momentum. The discussion around this point was centred on quantum computing. The most frequently cited barrier was the limited scale and quality of current quantum hardware. Several participants noted that the technology has not yet proven itself sufficiently in an operational setting, which is why many organisations in the energy sector are currently monitoring developments rather than actively building.

On the algorithmic side, very few quantum algorithms with promising end-to-end speed-ups are available for energy system problems. Current research efforts are mainly focused on applying existing (hybrid) quantum algorithms to power system problem reformulations, often as one-off proof-of-concept studies. Also, it remains unclear which power system problems are genuinely suited to quantum computation versus those better left to classical methods, or even how to recognise promising candidates in the first place. To this end, some participants advocated for application-oriented algorithm and hardware co-design that explicitly considers domain-specific requirements.

Skills gap and communication barriers

There was consensus that meaningful progress at the intersection between quantum technologies and power & energy systems requires access to multi-disciplinary expertise. This includes expertise in quantum engineering, algorithm design, software engineering, and power & energy systems.

Participants noted the lack of a sufficient number of researchers and practitioners who adequately understand both fields and the skills gap between quantum and energy domain experts. Moreover, to enable multi-disciplinary collaboration, some participants stressed the need for “people in the middle” or “translators” who can bridge quantum capabilities and power system needs.

Beyond the skills shortage itself, participants identified a related communication challenge between domain experts and non-experts such as managers and decision-makers. Those who understand the technology and its potential impact on the energy sector are not necessarily the people who define strategy or control investment decisions. For example, within energy companies it may be difficult to convince leadership of the need to explore quantum approaches as opposed to investing capital and personnel in other priorities such as Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Infrastructure access and cost

Commercial quantum hardware and computing infrastructure was found to be expensive, and access was reported as limited, especially for practitioners. Participants also identified the cost of upskilling personnel as a distinct, related barrier.

Lack of funding

Multiple participants from industry identified the difficulty in presenting a compelling business case and being aligned with industry’s expectation for short-term outcomes on pressing problems as a key barrier. This affects both industry investment in quantum technologies and the research funding landscape. From an

industry perspective, energy companies have no clear incentive to fund quantum research, pilots, or proof-of-concept studies. Investing in an unproven technology or co-financing research projects with uncertain returns is difficult to justify internally.

Participants from academia indicated a mismatch between technology readiness levels (TRL) and expectations of available funding instruments. As an emerging research domain, quantum technology applications for power & energy systems are typically viewed as too applied from a fundamental research funding perspective, and as too immature from an applied funding perspective, leaving a structural gap that hinders work in this area. This gap risks creating a competitive disadvantage for the Netherlands and Europe, not only in technological development and leadership, but also in scientific presence in this emerging field.

Question 4: Which stakeholders are essential to pursue the use cases identified in Questions 1 and 2?

Participants identified a broad stakeholder ecosystem spanning academia, industry, and the quantum technology sector itself (Table 2). For each stakeholder, participants were asked to consider the capabilities and value they bring, and the commitment required from them. Different groups emphasised different actors, but the clear consensus was that structured collaboration across sectors and domains is necessary to pursue impactful use cases.

A recurring point across groups was that stakeholder engagement needs to span multiple organisational levels: from C-level executives and strategic decision-makers down to engineers and researchers. Securing buy-in across the entire hierarchy, not just with technical teams, is essential both for boosting exploration, but also for moving from exploration to implementation.

Table 2: Identified stakeholders

Stakeholder	Examples	Role and contribution
Grid operators	Dutch TSO and DSOs, ENTSO-e, E.DSO	Use case owners, domain expertise, operational data; co-develop pilot / research projects, define use case requirements and success metrics
Energy companies	Energy providers, traders, large consumers (e.g., Eneco, Vattenfall, Essent)	
Technology providers / system integrators	E.g., Siemens, General Electric, PSI, Capgemini, Deloitte	Integration of quantum technologies into existing systems and workflows, consulting and advisory
Academia		Fundamental and applied research, human capital development
Applied research organisations & national infrastructure providers	TNO, SURF	Bridge fundamental and applications, facilitate academia-industry collaboration, provide access to computing infrastructure
Quantum technology companies & start-ups		Facilitate access to the latest quantum hardware and software stack, inform research and application vision; embrace the energy sector as an application domain
Funding agencies, national ecosystem coordinators & government	NWO, RVO, NERA, QDNL, 4TU, ACM	Create dedicated funding instruments / explicitly include power & energy systems as impactful use cases for quantum technology applications in their roadmaps, provide strategic coordination and regulation; reflect early-adoption potential and strategic interest in quantum technologies (e.g., defence)
Communication experts	Science communication offices, specialised consultancies	Convey the value proposition to non-specialist audiences and decision-makers

6. Call to action

The Energy Transition places stringent demands on the measurement, cybersecurity, and computational capabilities that underpin modern power & energy systems. The scale and complexity of the problems that need to be solved are growing faster than what current approaches can handle. Quantum technologies offer a complementary paradigm across all three fronts: computing for large-scale analysis, optimisation and data analytics, communications for future-proof cybersecurity of critical infrastructure, and sensing for high-precision monitoring of physical grid assets. **The window for shaping this field is open now.** Countries and regions that invest early in building the research base, workforce, and collaborative structures at the intersection of quantum and energy will be best positioned to capture the value these technologies create as they mature. The workshop participants see the Netherlands as highly competitive in both energy and quantum research in isolation, but not as a leader in this emerging interdisciplinary field. Given its strong quantum research ecosystem and pressing grid challenges, the Netherlands has both the opportunity and the reason to engage actively at this early stage and assume a leading position as the field matures.

Based on the Quantum4EnergyNL workshop, clear near-term and medium-term opportunities for research and development in quantum technologies for power & energy systems were identified. However, a set of barriers that risk slowing progress in this new field within the Netherlands has also been brought forward. Converting this potential into impact requires sustained engagement and strategic choices from stakeholders across research, industry, and government.

The following **recommendations** emerged from the discussions:

1. Invest in application-oriented quantum research

The structural TRL gap, which leaves this emerging research domain falling through the cracks between fundamental and applied funding instruments, needs to be addressed. Moreover, the discontinuation of large-scale national interdisciplinary research funding instruments such as NWO's "Perspectief" programme, which bridged the gap between fundamental research and the market introduction of new technologies, is particularly detrimental to progress in this area. Funding agencies should create dedicated instruments that support multidisciplinary, use-case-driven research programmes at the intersection of quantum technologies and power & energy systems. Alternatively, power & energy systems should be explicitly included in the scope of existing calls for proposals on quantum technology applications and, equally, quantum technologies should be recognised as an eligible method in existing Energy Transition calls.

2. Develop a multidisciplinary workforce

The single most consistently identified barrier across all workshop participants was the shortage of people who understand both quantum technologies and power systems. Human capital needs to be developed in parallel with the technology. Companies and universities should jointly

develop training programmes, industrial PhDs, secondment schemes, and student placements (e.g., MSc internships and thesis projects).

3. Engage stakeholders and establish structured collaboration

The participant profile makes clear that several key stakeholders were missing, e.g., quantum hardware developers and policy staff. Quantum4EnergyNL will work to engage them and communicate the strategic importance of building awareness on this topic today. Use case owners in the energy sector must take an active role rather than monitoring developments in the field. In return, researchers need to engage in multidisciplinary research with domain-specific requirements rather than treating energy as a quantum technology sandbox.

No single stakeholder can advance this domain alone. Quantum4EnergyNL can serve as a contact point and springboard for future activities in this emerging domain, helping to ensure that efforts across the Netherlands are aligned, visible, and grounded in power & energy system needs. We urge funding agencies to consider launching dedicated calls for proposals, and we invite industry stakeholders to assume an active role in growing this domain in the Netherlands through co-investment in relevant research.